

To teach or not to teach? Preferences for working conditions and the alternative career opportunities of pre-service teachers

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Summary

1. Declining educational quality and teacher shortages are among the most pressing challenges facing Flemish education. Increasing the transition from teacher education into the teaching profession among the strongest candidates could address both problems simultaneously.
2. We examine the role of job characteristics and alternative career opportunities in the career choices of pre-service teachers, with a particular focus on the strongest profiles.
3. About seven out of ten pre-service teachers perceive fewer opportunities for career advancement in teaching than in alternative occupations, which is especially discouraging for the highest-performing pre-service teachers.
4. Pre-service teachers place great importance on having autonomy over their curriculum; this preference is strongest among the highest-performing pre-service teachers.
5. In career choice, salary, workload, and opportunities for advancement prove to be at least as important as more idealistic motives such as working with young people.

1. Introduction

Education systems across the globe face an alarming challenge: the persistent shortage of qualified teachers. According to the OECD, nearly half of 15-year-olds attend schools affected by staff shortages, with disadvantaged communities being hit the hardest (OECD, 2023). This shortage is particularly acute among men, STEM teachers, and high-performing graduates—profiles that are crucial to ensure both the equity and quality of education. Yet, despite significant public investment in teacher training, a considerable number of pre-service teachers choose to pursue careers outside of education upon graduation (De Witte et al., 2024). This underutilization of trained professionals not only wastes resources but also deepens the staffing crisis in schools.

Addressing these shortages requires a deeper understanding of how pre-service teachers decide whether to enter the profession. Previous studies often focus on altruistic motivations such as the desire to help children or a passion for teaching (Fray & Gore, 2018; Heinz, 2015). While valuable, this perspective overlooks the fundamental trade-offs students make between teaching and other careers. This policy brief summarizes the paper by De Cort and De Witte (2025), conducted in Flanders, breaks new ground by combining economic theory with innovative empirical methods to better understand these career decisions.

Through carefully designed discrete choice experiments with over 200 final-year pre-service teachers, this study quantifies how working conditions—such as salary, workload, career prospects, and curricular autonomy—influence the decision to teach. By also accounting for the students' perceptions of alternative careers, the study reveals which job attributes matter most, and for whom. In

particular, it highlights the pivotal role of career advancement opportunities and curricular autonomy for attracting the best-performing pre-service teachers, offering crucial insights for policymakers seeking to improve both the quantity and quality of future teachers.

2. Data and Methodology

To understand how working conditions and alternative career opportunities shape the decisions of future teachers, De Cort and De Witte (2025) collected new and detailed data from over 200 final-year pre-service teachers in Flanders. The research combines survey data with the first discrete choice experiments (DCEs) among pre-service teachers. DCEs are a rigorous method that allows for a precise estimation of individual preferences. Unlike traditional surveys where respondents may rate all job aspects as "important," DCEs simulate real-world trade-offs, forcing participants to choose between hypothetical jobs with varying attributes. This approach generates meaningful estimates of how much value pre-service teachers place on specific job characteristics.

The first DCE presents pairs of generic jobs—teaching or otherwise—that vary in salary, workload, career opportunities, and the frequency of working with young people. This setup captures both idealistic motivations and pragmatic concerns. The second DCE presents only teaching jobs that differ in features specific to the teaching profession: autonomy over curriculum, support from colleagues, student behaviour, and salary. By including salary in both experiments, the study translates preferences into a common metric of “willingness-to-pay”—the salary increase someone would require to accept less favourable working conditions.

In addition to the choice experiments, the survey gathers information on pre-service teachers' perceptions of working conditions in teaching versus their preferred alternative career. Participants reported which non-teaching career they were most likely to pursue, and how they expected it to compare to teaching in terms of workload, advancement, and other features. By combining preference data with these individual perceptions, the study goes beyond hypothetical job scenarios to reveal how actual career comparisons influence the decision to teach.

3. Results

The findings challenge earlier literature about what drives career choices among future teachers (Fray & Gore, 2018; Heinz, 2015). While many assume that intrinsic motivations dominate, this study shows that practical working conditions—particularly salary, workload, and career advancement opportunities—are at least as influential as the opportunity to work with young people. Pre-service teachers are not immune to economic reasoning: they weigh the costs and benefits of a teaching career relative to other options. For example, the average pre-service teacher prefers a career that pays 9% more over a career in which they are frequently able to work with young people.

Career advancement emerges as a key factor. More than two-thirds of participants believe they would have better career advancement opportunities outside of teaching. The choice experiment also shows that the best-performing pre-service teachers attach the most importance to career advancement opportunities. This indicates that the current lack of career prospects in the teaching profession may deter the very candidates most likely to excel in the classroom.

Workload is also a decisive factor, but not necessarily to the detriment of the teaching profession. 56% of pre-service teachers expect to work at least as much or more in the other career they are most strongly considering than as a teacher. The effect of workload on the attractiveness of teaching is therefore less uniformly negative than the effect of career opportunities.

Curricular autonomy is another decisive factor. Pre-service teachers—again, especially the top performers—place high importance on being able to shape their teaching content. In fact, they value this freedom more than some monetary incentives. Policies that reduce curricular autonomy in the name of accountability may therefore have unintended consequences, making teaching less attractive to talented candidates.

4. Policy Recommendations

This study provides strong evidence that improving working conditions is essential not only to attract more teachers, but also to attract the best teachers—those with the highest potential to improve educational outcomes. Policy makers could act on three key areas:

Strengthen career progression pathways
Many pre-service teachers, especially the most promising ones, perceive teaching as a dead-end job compared to alternative careers. Ministries should develop clear, structured career ladders in teaching—such as lead teacher roles, mentorship tracks, or subject-area specialisations—that reward expertise and performance without requiring a move into school management. Transparent promotion mechanisms can help make the profession more attractive to ambitious candidates.

Protect and promote curricular autonomy

Top-performing candidates value the ability to shape what and how they teach. European and national policymakers who implement standardisation policies driven by test-based accountability might therefore attract less high quality teachers. While standardisation also has its benefits, trusting teachers as professionals allowing room for some autonomy can increase the attractiveness of the profession.

Address perceptions of teaching compared to alternative careers

Studies assessing the attractiveness of teaching often focus on actual working conditions. Our study highlights how career decisions are in fact driven by perceptions of these working conditions that need not be accurate. For example, we find that pre-service teachers substantially underestimate their future salaries and disagree on many facets of what a career as a teacher looks like such as the workload and amount of curricular autonomy. Providing accurate information about teachers' job characteristics could increase the attractiveness of teaching by changing some of these pessimistic expectations.

What schools can do

At the school level, leadership plays a vital role in shaping the day-to-day experience of teachers. Schools can offer mentorship and peer support structures, particularly for early-career teachers. They can also provide autonomy in lesson planning and teaching strategies. Finally, schools should foster a professional environment where strong performance is recognised, not taken for granted.

A European role for coordination and support

At the European level, the findings suggest a need to support member states through shared research, peer learning, and strategic

funding. EU initiatives could promote best practices in teacher career design and provide funding for pilot reforms that improve working conditions. The Horizon Europe programme and the European Education Area could prioritise innovation in teaching careers, alongside teacher recruitment and retention.

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